

Radio and Newspapers

What Intersections for Media History?

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Book of abstracts

About the Book of Abstracts

This book of abstracts is a compilation of texts provided by the authors for the Radio and Newspapers Conference. The conference took place at the University of Lausanne (Switzerland) on June 30 and July 1st, 2026 and was organized by the History Department of the University of Lausanne and the Impresso Project.

Abstracts are listed in the order of appearance in the program.

Each paper can be referred to independently or as a whole:

Ruppen Coutaz Raphaëlle, Grandjean Martin, Michelet Arthur and Düring Marten (eds). *Radio and Newspapers: What Intersections for Media History?*, Lausanne, 2026, 46 p. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.20813962](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20813962)

Conference website:

<https://impresso.github.io/radio-and-newspapers-conference/>

Illustration:

Journalists in the Radio-Canada/CBC newsroom in Montreal, 30 November 1944

Photo Conrad Poirier, Bibliothèque et Archives nationales du Québec, Wikimedia Commons.

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Radio and Newspapers: What Intersections for Media History?

University of Lausanne 30 June - 1 July 2026

Radio and Newspapers: What Intersections for Media History?

Conference call for papers

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Building on our ongoing reflections on a historical “transmedia” approach, this international conference—organized by the Impresso project and the History Department of the University of Lausanne—aims to move beyond the traditional understanding of press-radio relations. As the two main information media in the 20th century, their relationship has often been reduced in literature to one of simple institutional competition. This conference seeks to investigate the complexity of their relations. It aims to throw light on mutual influences over content and format, staff and practices circulation between the two media, as well as cross-representations and cross-uses. A central objective is to explore the novel research perspectives offered by the development of digital tools in the context of the digitization of press and radio archives.

*This initiative follows on from the conference “Transmedia History: Circulations, Reconfigurations and New Methodologies”, held in Lausanne in January 2025, whose Book of Abstracts is available online ([10.5281/zenodo.15052470](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15052470)). A special issue of *TMG Journal of Media History*, entitled “*Transmedia Histories*,” is also in preparation.*

Although recent years have seen proposals for more integrated approaches (transmedia, cross-media, media convergence, etc.), mass media historiography has long been constructed around compartmentalized views of each media. This is particularly true for press studies, where radio is rarely mentioned or only very sporadically (Delporte et al., 2016; Hampton, 2004; Koss, 1990). On the other hand, radio has been more often studied in relation to other media. This has been the case with television (TV), most notably in research on public broadcasting (Jeanneney, 1999; Drack, 2000; Mäusli and Steigmeier, 2006; Mäusli, Steigmeier, and Vallotton, 2011), but also with the press, due to its far-reaching influence during the early days of radio broadcasting (Arceneaux, 2019). Instances of studies on the relations of the press and radio primarily pertained to their rivalry. In the 1920s, the emergence of radio, capable of reaching audiences more rapidly, sparked concern among newspaper publishers. They attempted to curb its development, notably by claiming a monopoly on news gathering and imposing advertising restrictions to protect their commercial position. Some alternatively sought to oversee its development or even became station owners themselves (Stamm, 2011). This rivalry led to numerous institutional negotiations over time, such as during the liberalization of audiovisual broadcasting (Sandoz, 2025, 153-188). It persists to this day, most notably in recent debates around digital content production by public radio and TV broadcasting companies.

These central and significant tensions have dominated historiography, overshadowing those other forms of interaction between the press and radio which remain largely underexplored. The press and radio differ profoundly in terms of medium (written vs. oral), technological constraints, modes and means of production/distribution, and archiving conditions—which pose specific challenges for preservation, access, and joint analysis. Nonetheless, these two media have always evolved within what Siân Nicholas calls a “culture of intermediality” (2012). This culture manifests through stylistic

convergence, content interdependence (notably mutual borrowing), as well as staff circulation. Such a perspective invites us to envision “an integrated history of mass media,” focusing on interactions and co-evolutions between media throughout their development (Nicholas, 2012, 383).

The conference wishes to explore this “interlinked media history” (Nicholas, 2012, 383), the roots of which even predate the massification of radio (Arceneaux, 2014). We encourage research on complex interactions and interdependencies between the press and radio, so as to move past analyses of sole competition dynamics. The goal is to shed light on transmedia dynamics, mobilizing tools and approaches (e.g., digital methods) that can, more broadly, enrich theoretical and methodological reflections on media history. Our aim is to contribute to a de-compartmentalized and “entangled” history of the press and radio, understanding their development within a broader social, political, and cultural framework (Cronqvist and Hilgert, 2017).

To this end, we welcome contributions centered around three main research areas:

1. Content and Formats: Mutual Influences and Remediation Processes

This focus aims to identify and analyze the various ways in which the press and radio mutually influenced each other throughout the 20th century, both in terms of published/broadcast content and adopted formats. Moving beyond readings based solely on rivalry or competition, it seeks to explore interdependence, imitation, reappropriation, and reciprocal transformation. From the early days of radio broadcasting, publishers played an active role in creating and sponsoring programmes. News agencies were often the primary (or the sole) source of information for radio content. Besides, the radio drew heavily on newspapers to structure programmes and formats, such as with news bulletins or radio “magazines.” Nevertheless, influence was reciprocal. The press took on radio vocabulary and style to invigorate its own content, by even integrating discursive features typical of radio broadcasts. More broadly, aware that its readers were increasingly tuning into the radio for news, the press gradually adapted its content, redefining its role by focusing more on analysis and opinion. The very form of newspaper articles evolved: shorter headlines, lighter layouts, condensed paragraphs, all of which are changes attributed to the influence of radio’s concise formats, particularly news bulletins.

These mutual influences also manifest in the parallel evolution of specific formats. For instance, the interview genre, born in the press as an attempt to capture oral testimony, was transposed to radio with its own codes (Willem, 2020). Similarly, satire developed in both media, moving from printed caricatures to radio pastiches, just as advertising found specific expressions for each medium (Morillas, 2005). In some cases, formats moved to the point of complete media shifts. For instance, certain radio programmes gave rise to press titles (Kaenel, 2021).

The circulation of journalistic models and editorial practices illustrates the deep connections between the two media. Our first focus therefore aims to understand the mechanisms by which narratives are rephrased, reformatted, adapted, or reworked from one medium to another. The process, defined by Bolter and Grusin (2000) as “remediation,” shows how each medium exists within a network of imitations, diversions, and reinterpretations of other media. Although this concept was first used to describe phenomena peculiar to the digital era, it can apply to the historical relations of press and radio as well. New media do not supplant existing media; instead, they reconfigure and repurpose them, and integrate them into new expressive frameworks.

Contributions for this area might address the following questions:

- Which actors and which economic, political, and/or technical dynamics boosted or hindered such hybridization processes?
- How did editorial logics and material constraints influence the reconfiguration of formats?
- What transfers of style, vocabulary, genres, or rhythms can be observed between these two media?
- How does the concept of remediation renew the analysis of relations between media?

2. Actors and Practices: Circulations and Convergences

The second research area aims to examine movement between the press and radio, whether in terms of individual career paths or journalistic practices. It emphasizes circulation and convergence which, far from being marginal phenomena, profoundly structured media ecosystems long before the digital era. Individual career paths highlight the strong permeability of the two media (Valsangiacomo, 2015). Many professionals—columnists, editorialists, reporters, or sports, film and culture journalists—moved between media or worked simultaneously for both. Some radio directors or programme managers first came through the press industry. This mobility partook of the emergence of a “professional media community” (Nicholas, 2012, 388), characterised by intermedial staff circulation and the formation of social circles that reinforced interdependencies.

At the same time, professional practices were also subject to cross-appropriation. Media convergence, whether economic or technological (Sparviero, Peil, and Balbi, 2017), fostered the development of transferable know-how. These dynamics can be tracked in both past and contemporary journalistic practices. Early 20th-century experiments like the Chicago Daily News’s Radio Photologues testify to early forms of multimedia journalism, combining text, sound, and image (Good, 2017). This leads to considering convergence as a recurrent historical dynamic rather than a linear process emerging alongside digital technology. The interdependence of media is therefore not new in itself, but has accelerated and reshaped in recent years due to digital reformatting.

Proposals for this second area might address the following questions:

- How did the “journalist” identity evolve with the emergence of a new media, i.e. radio? How did the professional media community reorganize to adapt to, and integrate new occupations?
- What is the profile of individuals who embodied the convergence of press and radio? Did they follow standard or outstanding career paths?
- Moving past visible evidence found in media content, what are the underlying institutional and economic dynamics that drive press-radio convergence?
- How did digital convergence redefine the boundaries between radio and press, both in terms of editorial practices and production process?

3. Reciprocal Discourse and Representations: Towards a Hybridization of Uses

The third research focus pertains to the reciprocal representations that radio and the press produced of one another. It also broaches the cross-uses made by audiences. The goal is to better understand, on the one hand, how the press and radio—far from evolving in silos—defined themselves in relation to each other, and influenced one another symbolically. On the other hand, it seeks to examine the various ways in which their audiences made complementary uses of them.

Discourses produced by media about their competitors and partners offer a privileged terrain for observing intermedial dynamics. The press, for example, reported on radio early on through critiques, columns, or special pages. It thereby contributed to shaping the public image of radio broadcasting, while consolidating its own authority and responding to growing public interest in “entertainment” pages (MacLennan, 2012). Conversely, some radio programmes staged, cited, or analysed the press, further contributing to blurring boundaries between the two media. Cross-representations such as these testify to both a desire for competitive positioning and a logic of complementarity. Perceptions circulating between the two media offer keys to understanding how each of them legitimized their respective roles in the public sphere. Beyond discourses, the material forms of hybridization will be central to this research area. Radio magazines, radio press reviews, cross-promotional advertisements, or specialized outlets like *The Listener*, *Radio Times* or *Hör Zu* illustrate how one medium can be a platform to promote or narrativize the other. Commercial and institutional collaboration between press publishers and radio broadcasters, esp. for publishing programme schedules or supplements, played a formative role in structuring a hybrid media ecosystem.

The porosity between these two media spheres hints at the existence of a common culture. It also points out mutual adaptation to the norms and expectations of different audiences. This focus thereby seeks to examine convergent media usage practices within households. Cross-media consumption reveals that audiences navigate through a transmedia environment, investing different media in a complementary fashion, through simultaneous or sequential “convergent media use” (Müller and Röser, 2017).

Contributions for this area might address the following questions:

- How was the emergence of radio reported on and perceived by the press?
- How did these two media popularize, promote, or criticize the other’s content?
- How did the paper medium (newspapers) serve the objectives and interests of radio, and vice versa, how could the audio medium (radio) be used to serve the press?
- How did audiences engage with press and radio content in hybrid media environments?
- To what extent and in what volume do we observe convergent media use within households? How is this trend intensifying in the digital age?

By mobilizing a cross-cutting approach to the history of the press and radio, the contributions gathered in this conference will provide new insights into the history of both media. They will also explore novel perspectives offered by the massive digitization of archives and the development of computational methods for writing a transmedia history. They will further shed light upon the culture of intermediality in which these media have emerged and developed, without overlooking the differences, divergences and tensions which have occurred and persisted, notably in the face of numerous economic and technical challenges.

The objective of this scientific event is to contribute to the clarification and development of a transmedia approach in historical research. More broadly, it seeks to promote a de-compartmentalized history of the press and radio. We encourage submissions from junior and senior researchers who wish to share their empirical and methodological approaches in this field.

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"Best Comrades Ever to Have Met": How Editorial Broadcast Radio Services Catapulted Germany's Printed Press Into the Fast-News Age (1919-1943)

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This research examines "Pressefunk," a non-public broadcast technology used to transmit journalistic material from national news agencies to their provincial press subscribers. It became an innovative, yet somewhat quirky solution to an economic dilemma that defined the speed of German news distribution for twenty years.

In the age before teleprinters were widely available, broadcast radio catapulted the printed press into a fast-moving news age. While high-speed wire telegraphy had become a staple of the communications industry, the Reich Post's national monopoly kept it prohibitively expensive and cumbersome. Few newspaper publishers could afford a direct wire line, forcing agencies to rely on slower express mail for the bulk of their journalistic material. Only the landline telephone offered comparable speed. Journalists used the overburdened telephone systems so excessively that business customer groups lobbied the government for a pushback. Then broadcast technology arrived.

While few would see a future of radio as a journalistic news medium, it was instantly understood across the news and publishing industry that "wireless telephony" could be a grand leap forward in cost efficiency and competitiveness.

Early attempts by government radio pioneers like Hans Bredow (starting in 1919) to intertwine the established press with the young medium failed. It was a bad match and bad timing; the concept of centralized, state-run newscasting could not integrate the interests of Weimar Germany's press, which was highly fragmented, pluralistic, politically polarized, and deeply troubled by runaway inflation.

A successful second attempt materialized in 1924, shortly after general public radio went on the air. With competition driving compromise, three major news agencies became broadcast licensees serving their own subscribers in the press. They included the government-leaning Wolff's Telegraphic Bureau which cooperated with the national newspaper publishers' association, the Telegraphen-Union of the arch-conservative Hugenberg media conglomerate, and the Social Democratic Press Service (which, for its radio system, would become the envy of socialist parties across Europe). A few others were involved as junior partners. A foreign service was set up in a separate scheme.

Soon, press agencies put radio antennae in their own logos and trade advertisements while large and small newspapers everywhere raised real radio masts on their rooftops. Headphones became indispensable in the newsroom. A young profession—specialized "press stenographers"—was now glued to their radio instead of phone receivers. No print edition came out without the "latest radio reports." These new practices fueled a rapid increase in competition. As the newspaper publishers' trade journal rejoiced in 1925, "radio and the press are the best comrades ever to have met."

However, the two media had to bridge a divide: Newscasts delivered sound, not written text. The spoken word had to be manually recorded and transcribed at fixed times throughout the day. This process was error-prone, inflexible, and labor-intensive. The press accepted the disadvantages due to the lack of good alternatives.

The "Pressefunk" model persisted for nearly two decades, largely bypassing the extremely slow rollout of teleprinter technology. The rattling, bell-ringing teleprinter would play only a minor role until the 1950s. Instead, what replaced "Pressefunk" in 1943 was a different kind of broadcasting: the

Hell printer, a mix of fax and telegraphy that converted coded radio signals into printed text, without the need for recording staff.

This study utilizes original primary sources, including Bundesarchiv government ministry records, Reichs Post reports, and contemporary trade journals (such as *Zeitungs-Verlag*, *Deutsche Presse* and *Der Pressestenograph*), to document the technological, political, and economic evolution of this crucial news distribution model bridging radio and print.

"A Grave Danger to Everything Special in Our Civilization": The Welsh-Language Press and Radio in Wales in the 1920s and 1930s

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This paper responds to the question in the third strand of the call for papers and will address the question: How was the emergence of radio reported on and perceived by the press?

In his book, *Broadcasting and the BBC in Wales*, John Davies quotes Asa Briggs who stated that to write the history of broadcasting was to write the history of everything else. 'This is particularly true of Wales,' Davies argues, 'where, to a greater extent than perhaps in any other country in Europe, broadcasting has played a central role, both positive and negative, in the development of the concept of a national community.' Historian Aled Jones argues that this 'rested on a collectively held assumption that a medium of communication.....could play a major part in rescuing the Welsh language from its precipitous decline.'

The Welsh language, therefore, has played a major part in the shape and development of both the press and radio in Wales. When radio first came to Wales through the BBC, there were grave concerns in the Welsh-language press, that the new medium with its predominantly English-language output, posed a threat to the survival of the Welsh language and its attendant culture. This was fuelled by reports such as that published by the Welsh Board of Education in 1927 which stated that: 'Wireless is achieving the complete Anglicisation of the intellectual life of the nation. We regard the present policy of the British Broadcasting Corporation as one of the most serious menaces to the life of the Welsh language...' The situation was not helped by the placing of Wales within a 'West Region' (which included the west of England) in the BBC's Regional Scheme in 1930, a move which added fuel to the fire.

This paper will therefore examine the response of the Welsh-language press to the emergence of radio in the 1920s and 1930s and will consider its role in the eventual establishment of the BBC's Welsh Region in 1937.

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Media Picturing Media: Implications of Media Change, Media Competition, and Complementarity in the Reception of the New Medium of Radio in the Contemporary Press

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The proposed contribution examines discourses on media change and media competition and complementarity within the reception of a new medium. Formulated as a question and relating to the subject matter: To what extent are discursive negotiation processes of the new medium of radio in its early days in the 1920s and 1930s reflected in contemporary daily newspapers and radio magazines? The assumption is that media discourses are highly influential for the constitution and further development of a new medium, indeed that they characterize it together with its technical prerequisites (Schneider and Spangenberg 2002). With regard to the specific situation of early radio, the thesis is that it cannot be assumed that there was only an obvious competitive relationship between radio and existing media, but rather that the advantage-takings and conflicts of authority were exceedingly complex and differentiated. The press of the time provided a central platform for discussion about the potential and dangers of radio for other media, where various stakeholders, from media critics and technology enthusiasts to broadcasters, journalists, listeners, theater directors, music representatives, and many others, had their say on the new medium, in editorially curated texts, of course.

The concepts of *intermediality* (Müller 1996) and remediation (Bolter and Grusin 1999) are used as theoretical background to find out more about how old and new media interact with and against each other in times of media change and how this interaction is negotiated at the discursive level. This involves, not least, the question of how media observe and influence each other, and how media change manifests itself along the lines of media evolution and revolution (Kinnebrock et al. 2015; Grampp et al. 2008). Furthermore, the representation of broadcasting in the press is examined from a formal perspective and in terms of the specific mediality of newspapers and magazines. The thesis here is that media relations are not only evident at the textual discursive level, but also in the design of print media, which are forced to respond to the new medium.

The analysis corpus includes publications from Austrian daily and weekly newspapers, radio program and trade journals (including “Radio Wien”, “Radiowelt” and “Radio-Woche”). On the one hand, it comprises Viennese media aimed at an urban readership, supplemented by media from the Tyrol region (e.g., “Innsbrucker Nachrichten”, “Tiroler Grenzboten”, “Haller-Lokalanzeiger”), which represent more regional perspectives. The texts are examined on the basis of a media-historical approach and questions of media discourse and media cultural history. The presentation is framed by a methodological reflection on the different digital environments that were used to compile the corpus, with an attempt for an analysis that brings together digital and analog approaches.

This contribution is based on the author's dissertation project, which deals with the reception of Austrian radio broadcasting in its early days in the contemporary press, focusing primarily on the years from 1924 to 1934.

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"Ignore the Cries of the Uneducated Masses." A Debate Concerning Radio Broadcast Music Programming in the Interwar Period of Czechoslovakia Appeared in Political Newspapers and Listener Magazines

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The advent of radio broadcasting in interwar Czechoslovakia was associated with the search for its social role and suitable programming. Radio emerged as the first mass medium under complete state control to broadcast a programme for all social groups. Public discussions about broadcasting were not conducted on air, but in the press, which regularly published public criticism and responses from officials ever since broadcasting began in 1923. Throughout the 15 years of interwar broadcasting, the main topic of debate was the cultural role of the nascent medium. The debate revolved around the fundamental question of whether the primary objective of broadcasting should be the edification of the population in matters of elite culture, as espoused by state authorities and radio management, or whether it should serve the interests of listeners and licence holders by offering accessible, popular entertainment to the general public. The controversy surrounding the new medium was centred on questions of taste, elite dominance, the hierarchical division of culture, and its connection to social division and mutual distinction. Due to the existence of only single broadcast channel, broadcasting could not be tailored to individual social groups as existing media could. State control of radio was also linked to the possibility of independent radio news reporting, which the authorities opposed, as well as the use of the new medium for state propaganda. Moreover, this debate was reflected not only in the press but also in the popular culture of the time. For instance, this phenomenon has been observed in the context of popular theatre plays and utopian fiction.

The presentation will focus on analysing the debates that took place in periodicals in 1935, which culminated during the parliamentary and presidential elections. The collapse of the existing government bloc at that time led to mutual attacks, including criticism of the elitist approach in a radio programme. Pro-populist criticism was primarily led by right-wing (and fascisising) tabloid newspapers, while the existing educational line was more defended by the centrist and left-wing press. Radio management responded to the criticism in its programme magazine and anniversary publication. The debate was comprehensively covered, summarised and commented on by the fan magazine *Svět mluví* [The World Speaks], subtitled '*Magazine for Radio Listeners, Lovers of Gramophone Records, Friends of Good Films and Amateur Photography.*'

The following three discourses are analysed: (1) the elite discourse, which promotes the edification of the masses through listening to complex musical structures; (2) the populist discourse, which calls for popular musical entertainment to relax workers, farmers, traders and craftsmen; and (3) the compromise discourse of Radio management. The debate also included references to the more popular form of radio programming in neighbouring countries, particularly those German-speaking ones. These programmes were favoured by German speakers residing in border regions, and their discontent with Czechoslovakia provided Germany with justification for annexing the Czech lands in 1938/1939. A diverse range of political and economic actors, encompassing foreign entities, radio aficionados, and the general populace, engaged in this discourse within the medium of print media. However, the radio did not provide coverage of this debate (at least, no evidence has been found).

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From Distribution to Participation: Audience Practices Between Radio Frankfurt and the *Südwestdeutsche Rundfunkzeitung*

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This paper examines the intermedial relationship between Radio Frankfurt, one of the Weimar Republic's most experimental regional broadcasting stations, and its associated radio magazine, the *Südwestdeutsche Rundfunkzeitung* (SRZ). By treating these two media not as isolated forms but as parts of a shared transmedia assemblage, this paper explores how content, formats, and styles were reworked to transverse the boundaries of print and broadcast. Challenging the traditional narrative of press-radio rivalry, it argues that the relationship between Radio Frankfurt and the SRZ in the late 1920s and early 1930s reveals early efforts to reconceive mass media as participatory and dialogic rather than unidirectional.

Under Ernst Schoen's artistic direction, Radio Frankfurt became a center of avant-garde media experimentation. Collaborators such as Walter Benjamin and Bertolt Brecht theorized and tested ways to transform radio from a "distribution apparatus" into a "communication apparatus", envisioning a medium based on dialogue rather than one-way dissemination. Yet because few recordings from the period survive, our understanding of this experimental vision depends largely on textual sources. The SRZ therefore emerges as a privileged archive of this vision. Ostensibly a program guide, the magazine functioned as a material interface through which the station mediated and shaped its relationship with listeners, providing insight into a culture of intermediality that actively reconfigured both media's expressive capacities.

Published as a semi-official organ connected to but not controlled by the station, the SRZ did more than list daily programming and comment on scheduled broadcasts. It expanded radio's temporal and material reach by reproducing artworks discussed on air, by printing photographs of speakers and authors, and by integrating coverage of cinema, architecture, and other cultural fields. These editorial choices adapted the form and content of broadcasting into print by supplementing the aural medium with visual and textual elements. The magazine thereby fostered a transmedial sensibility, presenting media not as discrete spheres but as interconnected and mutually reinforcing.

Most importantly, the SRZ cultivated participation through formats originally associated with broadcast. Recurring listener columns, story competitions, feedback features such as "Wie sag ich's meinem Sender?", and voting contests like *Wettsingen* exemplify how formats and address styles migrated across media. The frequent use of second-person address in print mirrored radio's rhetorical strategies, simulating dialogue and inviting active reader-listener engagement. Such practices transformed audiences into co-creators, decision-makers, and sources of data, subtly undermining the hierarchical sender-receiver model.

Drawing on Jonathan Sterne's understanding of media as sets of social practices and Alexander Galloway's critique of interfaces, this paper conceptualizes the SRZ as an active component within a broader radiophonic dispositif. By imagining radio as a multimedia assemblage linking loudspeakers, paper, postal networks, radio stations, and reader-listeners, the paper shows how Radio Frankfurt and the SRZ together pioneered early forms of transmedia practice. These practices involved not only cross-media circulation of content but also formal and stylistic adaptations to activate dialogue and participation. Ultimately, this case demonstrates the value of a transmedia perspective for writing media history beyond technological determinism, highlighting the socially and materially situated

strategies through which Radio Frankfurt under Schoen attempted to enact a participatory public sphere.

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Making Radio Music Visible: Lexical and Iconographic Mediation of Musical Listening in Spain's *Ondas* Magazine (1925-1935) - The LexiMus Project

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The introduction of radio broadcasting in Spain during the 1920s transformed musical listening practices, inaugurating a "disembodied" auditory experience that challenged traditional models of in-person music reception. While the history of listening has emerged as a fertile field of musicological research (Johnson, 1995; Thorau & Ziemer, 2018), and while radio's relationship with newspapers has often been examined through the lens of institutional competition, the visual and lexical dimensions of radio–press convergence remain underexplored. This paper examines how *Ondas* magazine (1925–1935, 493 issues), the official organ of Unión Radio—Spain's national broadcasting network—developed specific lexical and iconographic strategies to mediate radio's disembodied sonic experience, operating beyond competition as a complementary transmedia device. *Ondas*, like other contemporary magazines such as *Radio Times*, *Radio Digest*, *Radio Broadcast*, or *Radio Magazine*, played a central role in promoting radio broadcasting through the print media.

Research questions and methodology

This study addresses three interconnected questions: How did a radio-affiliated magazine construct a "listening public" (Lacey, 2013) through print media? What role did visual iconography play in mediating invisible radiophonic sound? What specialized lexicon emerged to name, describe, and guide this new form of listening?

Drawing on the complete digitized collection of *Ondas*, this research employed a mixed-methods approach combining quantitative corpus analysis with close readings of textual and visual materials. The study systematically analyzed a corpus of more than 1,500 images classified into nine thematic categories, as well as the complete set of music criticism and program notes from the sections "Notas musicales" ("Musical Notes") and "A través del micrófono" ("Through the Microphone"). Although *Ondas* included a wide variety of visual materials—ranging from cinema and theater to advertising and popular culture—this study focuses exclusively on images directly related to music.

The digital corpus was enhanced through optimized OCR data from the Biblioteca Nacional and the automatic extraction of all music-related content from each issue of *Ondas*. Textual analysis was conducted using both distant reading methods (Moretti, 2000) and close reading of selected materials, allowing for an integrated perspective that combines large-scale quantitative patterns with qualitative interpretation. This methodological combination underscores the potential of digital humanities tools for historical musicology.

Cross-media mediation devices

The magazine deployed a sophisticated apparatus of visual and textual mediation to constitute what we argue is a pioneering audiovisual artifact in Spanish music history. Most striking is the systematic iconographic program centered on illustrator Augusto's modernist drawings, which comprise more than 150 works.

Published weekly alongside opera broadcasts, these illustrations functioned as "visual listening guides," translating the codes of musical modernity into accessible graphic language. By providing visual form to the invisible sonic experience, this iconographic program anticipated contemporary audiovisual culture by several decades.

Complementing these artistic interpretations, *Ondas* invested heavily in photographic representation, publishing images of composers, performers, and singers. This extensive commitment to portraiture reveals a paradox at the heart of radio's mediation: the magazine sought to "embody" radio's inherently disembodied music. By providing faces and bodies to voices transmitted without physical presence, these photographs operated as a compensatory strategy, materializing the radiophonic through visual means. The magazine thus inhabited an intermediate space between sound and image, making the invisible auditory experience tangible.

Beyond the visual, *Ondas* developed specialized textual practices to guide this new form of listening. The analytical texts accompanying principal broadcast works—particularly in the sections "Notas musicales" and "A través del micrófono"—constructed a lexicon specifically adapted to mediated audition.

Transmedia convergence beyond competition

Quantitative analysis of the complete corpus reveals a systematic editorial strategy sustained across the decade. Rather than merely illustrating radio programming, *Ondas* completed it as a listening device, operating in the intermedial space between word and image to give material form to the radiophonic. The magazine did not compete with broadcasting; it constituted an integral component of the radio experience itself—a historical transmedia artifact *avant la lettre*.

With consistent musical content across 493 weekly issues, *Ondas* deployed vocabulary, interpretive descriptions, and visual apparatus that configured what can be considered Spain's first audiovisual artifact for music. This case study challenges traditional narratives of radio–press competition, demonstrating instead a model of convergent mediation in which print culture actively shaped radio's listening publics.

Expected results and contributions

By examining how *Ondas* deployed visual culture to mediate radio's acousmatic experience—sound divorced from visible source—the study illuminates the multisensory strategies through which early broadcasting constituted its publics. The quantitative analysis of images across 493 issues provides a replicable methodology for studying visual–textual corpora in digitized magazine collections, demonstrating how large-scale digital archives enable new perspectives on historical media practices.

Developed within the framework of the LexiMus project (*Lexicon and Ontology of Music in Spanish*), this research advances both media history and the historical study of Spanish musical vocabulary, revealing how specialized lexicons emerge at the intersection of technological change and cultural practice.

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Broadcasting Modernity: Radio, Print and the Making of a Colonial Soundscape in French Cochinchina

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This paper examines the intersections between radio broadcasting and print culture in colonial Cochinchina, through a combined historical and computational analysis of two under-studied corpora: *Radio-Saigon*, published by la Compagnie franco-indochinoise de radiophonie from 1930, and *Radio-Dakao*, a short catalogue in Vietnamese published in 1931.

While radio studies in colonial contexts have often focused on institutional infrastructures, political uses, or the diffusion of technical modernity, far less attention has been given to the textual artefacts that mediated radio for everyday audiences - program listings, advertising pages, and technical explanations published in both magazines and monographies. These documents offer a unique entry point into the translation and circulation of technical terminology into Vietnamese during a period of rapid linguistic and technological change.

Methodologically, this contribution explores whether multilingual embeddings developed by *Impresso* project can support cross-media and cross-lingual querying. Containing both French and Vietnamese segments, *Radio-Saigon*, together with *Radio-Dakao*, which translates or paraphrases numerous technical notions for a primarily Vietnamese readership, constitutes an ideal test case for evaluating the capacity of multilingual vector spaces to identify semantic equivalences, terminological shifts, and translated radio-technical lexicons. Preliminary experiments evaluate whether embeddings can retrieve aligned expressions for components such as “émetteur,” “antenne,” “ondes courtes,” “lampes,” or “modulation,” despite differences in orthography, terminology, or diachronic noise.

In parallel, the study aims to apply named-entity recognition (NER) to capture actors that operate across radio and print ecosystems: broadcasting institutions, commercial brands advertising receivers or batteries, and individuals mentioned as programme hosts, performers, or technicians. Mapping these entities across the two corpora makes it possible to visualise zones of overlap - points at which the press amplifies radio culture, radio incorporates printed references, and commercial advertising circulates across platforms.

Ultimately, this paper argues that such hybrid medias provides crucial element for understanding how auditory technologies were integrated into the colonial public sphere, not only through broadcasts themselves but also through their printed mediations.

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Comparing News in Print and Broadcast Media: An Exploratory Digital Analysis of Swiss Press and Radio

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Introduction

How does the medium influence the type of information presented? Does radio, constrained by its audio format, with programming schedules that leave little room for news and often limited by rules designed to prevent it from competing with print newspapers, present different information to its listeners than the press? And if there is a difference, is it primarily a purely quantitative one—with topics covered in greater detail in the media that has more space or airtime—or is it a different selection/prioritization of topics?

The aim of this paper is to lay the groundwork for a systematic and quantitative study of the news content of the press and radio in French-speaking Switzerland during the 20th century. While these media and their respective information policies have already been studied in their own right (Drack 2000, Clavien 2017), the challenge is to take advantage of recent digitization campaigns to ask these questions afresh, based on the archives themselves and explore the possibilities of digital media history (Balbi 2011, Michael and Werner 2024). This approach will highlight both the potential and the limitations of digital methods applied to these press and radio contents, and will enable discussion of the potential for comparison between very comprehensive press collections and radio archives, which are inevitably incomplete.

The physical space allocated to information: airtime and newspaper surface area

In French-speaking Switzerland, the place of news on the radio is heavily influenced by the fact that public service radio stations belonging to *Radio Suisse Romande* (RSR, which had a monopoly for decades) are strictly dependent on news bulletins from the Swiss Telegraphic Agency (ATS) for a long time. This is to prevent public radio from competing with private newspaper publishers. But beyond this short, regular news bulletin, RSR also devotes part of its airtime to current affairs programs. In the same way that journalistic news content is buried among a mass of other types of articles in a newspaper, is it possible to reconstruct the evolution of the place of news on the radio? Following the example of Aubry et al. (2005, 40–56) and MacLennan (2005) we sample the magazine *Le Radio* (later *Radio TV Je vois tout*) to reconstruct the radio schedules of French-speaking Switzerland between 1920-1980 in order to assess the overall proportion of news content, which we then compare to a similar sample from two newspapers in the same region, digitized on the Impresso platform (Ehrmann 2021). This enables us to discuss the conditions for such sampling, the challenges of classifying the types of content broadcast on the radio and featured in newspaper columns, and to initiate a reflection on the cross-media comparability of these results.

Analyzing the content of spoken news and the press: what overlaps?

While our first approach shows the context and density of information in the press and on the radio, this second part seeks to question the actual content of media coverage of news events. The aim is therefore to create a corpus of radio news recordings and newspaper articles covering the same geographical area and period in order to see how similar the topics covered are and whether either medium makes a particular selection. We therefore take the RSR archives for a given month and use speech-to-text technology to extract texts that are then embedded with the corresponding press

articles. The resulting semantic proximity map (Michelet and Grandjean 2026) allows us to document the correspondences but also, and above all, the differences, and to discuss the effect of the incompleteness of the radio archives on potential more systematic and larger historical press/radio studies.

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The Structures of Banking News on the Radio and in Newspapers in French-Speaking Switzerland

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Banks are routinely, if not daily, present in mass media without necessarily making headlines. While banking news has received attention from scholars in media studies and economics (Strauss and Vliegthart 2017, Toms 2019, Arnold 2020), historians have largely failed to address its overarching structures. Most efforts to assess the presence of banks in the news have focused on exceptional events such as financial crises, crashes, and scandals (Campbell et al. 2012, Reveley and Singleton 2013, Shaw 2019, Fleming et al. 2024, Wendschlag 2025). Furthermore, research has adopted a monomedia approach, focusing on newspapers alone. As a result, we know little about when and how mass media give attention to the banking sector. Likewise, it remains unknown whether news coverage of banking affairs reflects pure macro-economic realities—the state of the industry—or is shaped by implicit frames. This shortcoming is significant, given that mass media such as newspapers and radio have a “manipulative and gatekeeping power” and play a formative role in the making of “organizational legitimacy” (Palazzo and Scherer 2006). This paper offers the first systematic, transmedia analysis of banking news in historical perspective, focusing on radio and newspapers in French-speaking Switzerland. It uses a dataset of newspaper articles retrieved through the Impreso database and radio archives from the then-monopolistic public broadcaster RTS, covering a time spanning from 1 January 1960 to 31 December 1989. While radio data comes exclusively from RTS, four newspapers representing different orientations (liberal, conservative, trade-unionist, and generalist) were selected to ensure representativeness. This fine-grained analysis of banking news is based on a four-fold typology, looking at topic, context, position, and tone. By combining qualitative analysis of (often scarce) radio archives with quantitative, computational analysis of newspaper data, this paper provides a novel approach to understanding the structures of banking news across two key mass media, thereby contributing to historical research on the public perception of banks.

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Prima Pagina: Daily Press on the Radio

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This intervention aims to reconstruct the origins and characteristics of a long-running Italian radio program, *Prima pagina*, which began in 1976 on Radiotre and is still on the air today. It was the first radio program to offer a strong hybridization and exchange between the press and radio news: it is a radio press review, conducted each week by a different print journalist, followed by a direct dialogue with listeners.

As Nicoletta Verna writes in the entry dedicated to the program in the *Encyclopedia of Radio*, *Prima pagina* played a central role in revising the role of Rai Tre, Rai's traditional cultural channel, which under Forcella's direction expanded its target audience. At the same time, however, it has always enjoyed 'excellent ratings not only among the general public, but also in political, economic and financial circles, quickly becoming one of the pillars of Radiotre's programming'.

The birth of the program will be analyzed bearing in mind three central aspects in the history of Italian media: the 1975 Rai reform, the birth of local radio and television stations—sometimes linked to newspapers—and, finally, the story of the program's creator, then director of Radio Tre, Enzo Forcella, who had long experience as a political journalist in the print media. For this reason, the largely unpublished Forcella archive will be used, which contains some notes dedicated to the program.

The proposal, therefore, covers all three main themes of the conference, allowing us to reflect on an original and successful format – which, in the history of Italian public radio, became a characteristic model of Radiotre – but also on the actors of this hybridization and the way in which radio and daily newspapers represent and describe each other.

The analysis of *Prima pagina* is also particularly interesting in capturing a moment of profound transformation in the Italian media system in the second half of the 1970s: at that time, both radio and television and the daily press were undergoing profound changes. The former was changing thanks to the emergence of 'free' radio and local stations, which innovated languages and formats, also leveraging the protagonism of listeners who participated in broadcasts via telephone. The latter saw the emergence of new newspapers such as *Il giornale* (1974), *La Repubblica* (1976) and *L'occhio* (1979), which changed the landscape of daily newspapers by introducing the model of the popular daily newspaper (*L'occhio*) or a format that would be defined as a 'party newspaper' (in particular *La Repubblica*) to Italy. Moreover, the centrality and importance of the daily press in Italy in the second half of the 1970s is underlined by the use of newspapers in schools and the publication of books that taught students how to read newspapers, also aimed at a student audience.

The birth of *Prima pagina*, therefore, took place within the context of a profound transformation of the media system in Italy, with radio and daily newspapers playing an unprecedented leading role. It is therefore believed that this perspective, which is unprecedented because there are no specific studies on the subject, can make a significant contribution to the analysis of the relationship between radio and newspapers.

The presentation will be the result of original research which, in addition to reconstructing the historical and media context, will make use of the Rai archive and unpublished sources, such as the aforementioned Forcella archive.

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Stunde der Frau: From Page to Air – The Remediation of Women's Journalism in Interwar Austria

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This paper examines "Stunde der Frau" (1925–1927), Austria's first women's radio programme, as an example of early press and radio convergence in Austria. It explores how established newspaper formats and topics, particularly women's pages, were translated into a radio format, revealing processes of remediation, text reuse, and stylistic exchange between print and broadcast journalism. The research also investigates who the presenters were and how they incorporated radio features into their broader cross-media practice. Together, these questions situate "Stunde der Frau" (Woman's Hour), within the evolving media culture of interwar Austria, where journalistic practices, actors, and formats intersected and mutually influenced one another.

Press studies rarely address radio, while broadcasting history focuses on institutional development or later links to television. This paper highlights creative exchanges between press and radio. "Stunde der Frau" shows early broadcasting did not replace print culture but reconfigured it within what Siân Nicholas calls a "culture of intermediality", where media evolve through interaction rather than isolation.

On 1 October 1924, Austria's first radio broadcaster, RAVAG, went on air. Between 1925 and 1927, it aired the weekly programme 'Stunde der Frau', aimed at a female audience. Little is known about its earliest broadcasts and its first presenter, Else Stephani, introduced simply as "Frau Else". After a few months, the programme was reformulated and continued for more than eighty episodes before being discontinued. Around forty-four Viennese personalities (including physicians, psychologists, scholars, and fashion journalists) delivered lectures on a wide range of topics. In contrast to the often-anonymous authorship of women's pages in newspapers, these presenters were recognized public figures who brought professional authority to the microphone. The majority regularly published in Viennese newspapers or gave public lectures, underscoring the permeability between the journalistic and broadcasting spheres.

The emergence of 'Stunde der Frau' can be understood within the dispositif of popular women's pages in daily newspapers. These sections offered a broad mix of content – from fashion to cooking, health, childcare, and needlework – combining entertainment with moral and educational guidance. A comparable thematic range characterised 'Stunde der Frau', which translated these instructive and gendered formats into the auditory realm. The programme thus exemplifies what Bolter and Grusin have termed 'remediation': the process by which a new medium refashions and recontextualises older ones. In this case, radio remediated the conventions of print journalism, transforming women's pages into performative speech.

One of the main sources for this study consists of the RAVAG magazine 'Radio Wien', which from 1925 also published supplementary material accompanying 'Stunde der Frau'. These texts not only document the programme's content but also show how the radio medium engaged in self-mediation through print, extending listening experiences into reading practices. Since no audio recordings do exist, 'Radio Wien' functions as a crucial intermedial archive, bridging sound and text, performance and publication. By comparing these materials with the speakers' publications and contemporaneous newspaper women's pages, the study traces parallels in topic selection, structure, highlighting the transformation of written journalism into oral performance.

Methodologically, the paper combines media-historical and comparative analysis to examine how journalistic practices circulated between print and broadcast forms. The speakers of 'Stunde der Frau', illustrate early examples of professional mobility and the transfer of journalistic practices across

media. Their participation demonstrates how credibility and authority, long associated with the printed word, were rearticulated through voice, tone, and presence on air. 'Stunde der Frau' thus offers insight into how early radio relied on the authority of the press to shape its own identity and legitimacy.

By examining the remediation of women's pages to new medium radio, the study reveals how press and radio coexisted within a shared communicative culture that fostered exchange and professional circulation. It shows that early Austrian radio features did not emerge as an autonomous medium but as part of an interlinked media system in which formats, practices, and audiences overlapped. Ultimately, the programme illustrates how the logics of print were reinterpreted through sound, performance, and immediacy – an early instance of multi-media journalism.

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Pour une histoire croisée des magazines féminins, de la presse écrite à la radio

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Si l'histoire de la presse féminine française ou francophone a fait l'objet de plusieurs études historiques, la question des émissions destinées à un public féminin demeure en grande partie inexplorée. Plus encore, les liens entre les magazines féminins de presse écrite et les émissions radiophoniques destinées à une audience féminine restent largement méconnus. En dehors de la figure de Méné Grégoire, qui a officié d'abord dans des colonnes de presse écrite avant de rejoindre le micro de Radio Luxembourg en 1967 puis les pages de *Marie-Claire* dès 1968, les circulations de professionnel·le·s et de dispositifs d'un support à l'autre restent à étudier.

L'objectif de cette contribution consistera à poser des jalons pour une histoire croisée des magazines féminins, de la presse écrite à la radio, afin d'observer les circulations entre les deux médiums, les effets de concurrence et les influences réciproques, de l'entre-deux-guerres aux années 1980. Tandis que les premières rubriques radiophoniques destinées aux femmes ont été directement inspirées des magazines féminins de l'entre-deux-guerres, la mise en ondes de tels programmes a nécessairement influencé et transformé la presse féminine.

Située au croisement de l'histoire des médias, de l'histoire de la presse et de l'histoire du genre, cette contribution s'inscrit dans le cadre d'une recherche au long cours sur l'histoire des émissions féminines et des femmes professionnelles de radio et des médias.

L'approche transmédiatique adoptée autour de la radio et de la presse écrite tendra aussi, dans une certaine mesure, à prendre en compte les liens avec le médium télévisuel – à partir de l'émergence des émissions féminines TV dans les années 1950.

Plusieurs aspects seront observés et analysés dans cette contribution :

- Les circulations multiples entre les magazines féminins radiophoniques et de presse écrite, qu'il s'agisse des circulations de professionnel·le·s ; de types de rubriques ou de dispositifs (par exemple le recours au courrier des lectrices / auditrices et leur exploitation) ; de personnalités invitées...
- Les thématiques traitées au fil du temps entre les deux médias, dans une perspective d'étude croisée, en observant si certains sujets ont tendance à émerger d'abord plutôt sur les ondes ou inversement. En filigrane, la question du rôle tantôt émancipateur tantôt normatif de ces magazines sera évoquée
- L'évocation et la représentation des magazines féminins et des professionnel·le·s du média concurrent sur chacun des deux supports
- La réception de ces journaux et émissions féminines
- Par ailleurs, une attention sera portée à la représentation de ces magazines féminins dans la presse et les médias traditionnels

Sans avoir l'ambition de proposer une étude exhaustive du sujet sur le temps long de la période étudiée, il s'agira de poser des jalons pour une histoire croisée des magazines féminins entre les deux médiums. L'analyse s'appuiera sur l'étude de numéros des magazines féminins (notamment *Confidences*, *Marie-Claire*, *Elle*), d'archives radiophoniques, de journaux de programmes radio, mais aussi d'archives de presse traditionnelle, et d'un corpus d'émissions de télévision.

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Rejuvenating the Children's Sphere: Peregrinations Across Children's Media in Bengal, 1939-1955

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Scholarship in recent years has complicated the imagination of the fields of literary production and of broadcasting, showing how these cannot be regarded as separate spheres of analysis (Hendy 2018, Morse 2020). Yet radio modernism's focus has almost always been on the global north as the site of production and distribution even if the 1920s saw a change in reading and aural experiences even in contexts like South Asia. The proposed paper looks at a niche sphere in one region in colonial and early postcolonial India - interactive children's media which emerged in Bengal during the 1940s. Exploring the circulation of actors connecting press and radio initiatives for children and their simultaneous appearance in both, it reveals how these initiatives shaped each other from the beginning and allowed them to navigate their connection with the field of literary production for children.

A few years before India's independence some vernacular newspapers in Calcutta launched children's pages which promised to connect readers with a larger public culture. The popularity of these weekly pages coincided with the turn towards interactive children's programming of the All India Radio's (AIR) Calcutta station. While the two initiatives differed in the degree of state control and their interactive affordances, archives reveal a network of actors who moved between children's radio and children's print. Drawing from scholarship which emphasizes radio's connections with literary production (Wagner 2019), the article charts the connections of literary figures with children's media in a context where juvenile literature had long been a site of promoting nationalist sentiments (Sen 2004). It further looks at musical persona and a younger cohort of media workers who navigated across print and radio. This focus allows the paper to draw attention to legacy media's practice of nurturing ties with regional writers and singers in late colonial, early postcolonial India and allows it to move away from conversations around the BBC model's significance for Indian programming (Thiranagama 2010) and move beyond discussions about imperial/national control of broadcast media - an approach that predominates radio historiography in South Asia.

Drawing from the findings of a project funded by the Indian Council of Social Science Research in 2024 the paper focuses on two of the first children's pages published by the vernacular press from undivided Bengal: *Anandamela* and *Chhotoder Pattari* as well as interactive radio programmes for children from the Dacca and Calcutta stations. Primarily using data mined from listings in AIR's magazines, reportage and guest columns in children's pages and memoirs by media-workers, it explores the peregrinations of actors across print and radio initiatives for children.

The paper shall focus on: 1) how the movements of actors across children's press and radio might have influenced the format of these initiatives in the 1940s and 1950s; 2) How multivalent identities of actors as poets, writers, singers, editors or as radio-workers (*radiokarmi*) influenced their transmedial circulation and emerged as a consequence of this movement.

Following the trajectory of primarily three key figures: Bimal Ghosh and Akhil Neogi - editors of the children's pages, and Indira Debi - host of AIR Calcutta's *Shishumahal* it will reflect on the consequences of these intermedial jaunts. The paper by drawing attention to the networks and mobilities of media workers for children will argue that children's interactive print and children's radio were essentially connected enterprises and that the interactive format necessitated this intermedial circulation to garner public interest, rejuvenate existing shows or pages, and provide creative outlets for editors/comperes whose signature ventures imposed certain limitations on them. It will also show how actors who were relatively less established within the literary world brought these circulations to bear on their conflicted relationship with juvenile literature since the late 1930s

when as young aspiring writers they had started watching each other to understand what media-work and more specifically media for children might constitute.

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Entanglements Between Commercial Radio Stations and Magazines in the Long Sixties

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Throughout the 'Long Sixties', both Radio Luxembourg and Europe n°1, two well-known commercial radio stations (or radios périphériques in French) of the period, actively sought to offer their listeners une offre plurimédia (Blandin, 2013) by working with magazines. Helped by radio's secondariness (Chignell, 2009), this intermedial dimension of the broadcasters became a central component of their wider commercial dispositif in the 1960s (Legay, 2023). By focusing on commercially-driven and transnational broadcasters, this proposed contribution will offer insights into the complexity of transmedia relations in which both radio stations actively worked, exchanged, and collaborated with the press (more precisely, youth magazines) to compete with other broadcasters.

To do so, this contribution will examine the links, ties, and media 'entanglements' (Cronqvist & Hilgert, 2017) between the English service of Radio Luxembourg and the Fabulous 208 magazine, and between the magazine Salut les Copains ! and its eponymous show on French-speaking Europe n°1 in the 1960s; and between the four media overall. Thanks to a large digitised historical bilingual corpus of radio recordings and of issues of the youth magazines, the analysis focuses on the strong processes of mutual influences and exchanges between the radio programmes and the magazines to develop a 'culture of intermediality' (Nicholas, 2012) specific to commercial media. Therefore the proposed paper will directly participate in the first main research area of the conference: 'Content and Formats: Mutual Influences and Remediation Processes.'

In terms of the structure, the contribution will first analyse the historical links between the radio stations and the magazines to better set the transnational and transmedia context of the 1960s. Then, it will detail the ways through which commercial radio expanded some of its key features (such as irreverence, playfulness, interactivity, localism, etc.) into the pages of the magazines to generate a specific 'culture of intermediality'. A last part of the contribution will show how the cross-media dynamics were essential for the commercial radios' efforts to generate a highly visual culture, rooted in stardom culture, and to turn their listeners into creative consumers.

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Media Consumption in Hungarian Villages During the Socialist Era

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In Eastern Europe, communist regimes attached great importance to the role of various media (press, radio, television) in shaping consciousness, educating people, transmitting culture, and spreading propaganda. In Hungary, a vigorous campaign was launched in the 1950s and 1960s to encourage the peasantry, who were the least involved in media consumption, to become regular users, since their effectiveness depended on broad sections of society becoming consumers. This was promoted by the concept of culturedness ('kulturnost'), which was adapted from the Soviet Union. It summarised the behaviour that socially mobile peasants should adopt in their new urban environments. In the Hungarian context, the press mainly targeted rural residents, publishing countless articles in the 1950s and early 1960s that described the characteristics of a cultured person. According to these guidelines, a cultured person educated themselves through regular reading, listening to the radio, and later, watching television. A 1949 article in the national weekly newspaper "Szabad Föld", which focused on the peasant readership, put it this way: 'Listening to the radio is as much a part of the concept of the modern cultured man today as well as reading newspapers or using soap.'

In my presentation, which is based on the concept of culturedness, I will demonstrate how the contemporary press promoted newspaper reading and radio listening among rural inhabitants. I will also describe the campaigns organised to increase the number of rural subscribers, as well as how these efforts were represented in the press. Furthermore, I will outline the content and programmes intended to appeal to rural audiences, and the modes of reception that emerged in this respect. I will discuss the common characteristics of the press and radio rooted in peasant cultural consumption, such as group usage, the continuity of topics of interest to peasants across media and the difficulty of communicating new content. Although the media sought to influence tastes and bring peasant culture closer to urban culture, both media had to consider the needs of peasants to reach them as an audience. Readers and listeners preferred thematic content relevant to their everyday lives (e.g. weather reports, descriptions of handicrafts and agricultural advice), as well as formats similar to folkloric genres (narratives, poems and humorous writings). Alongside valuable programming content on radio and in print, less high-quality popular content also had to be tolerated. Furthermore, adapting certain genres (e.g. calendars) and language styles (e.g. sensational reporting and simple wording) to convey new socialist content seemed more effective than neglecting such content. The most important source material for my research comprises contemporary press articles on the subject and documents preserved in the archives of Hungarian Radio and Television.

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Radio Free Europe and the Socialist Press: A Paradoxical Interaction

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This paper seeks to explore the interaction between the written press and the radio journalism during the Cold War. Radio Free Europe was a transnational broadcaster created at the beginning of the Cold War in order to fight the informational monopoly of socialist states' media within the countries beyond the Iron Curtain. It claimed to provide the “captive audiences” with truth, in opposition with the “lies” from the socialist press. Aside the complex philosophical problematics posed by such normative pronouncements themselves, the most interesting fact about RFE was that its core *modus operandi* involved a hermeneutic yet politically loaded reading of the socialist press that it actually tried to counter. The paper that I am proposing therefore engages with the issue of “remediation” as an act of mutual influence at the level of content and format, since some programs were literally made after the model of certain media formats from within the socialist press or relied on airing press releases from both Western and Eastern news agencies. It however asks questions that connects politics and journalistic hermeneutics to those of the “medium” itself. In this sense, it investigates the paradox of designing “alternative” radio programs by producing counter-narratives to the articles that constituted their main sources of facts and knowledge about communism. The radio broadcasts were ideologically opposed to the press and yet derived their subjects from them. The paper deals with how that was possible by doing a close analysis of the clipped press articles that RFE archived and used in its broadcasts. In some cases, RFE documentarists kept program transcripts together with clipped items, thus allowing this type of interpretative analyses that mingle media archeology with discourse analysis and conceptual history.

While doing this meta-epistemic work, this contribution attempts to also come up with a few ideas about that could revise current assumptions about the Cold War media polarized informational landscape. It also questions the asymmetries in the different projects of digitizing the press articles from Central and Eastern Europe, which could actually reproduce a Cold War situation of over-representing media output the silences of which are obscured again.

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Itinéraire d'une figure médiatique totale : Le critique musical Émile Vuillermoz, de la presse à la radio... à la presse

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En France, la mise en place graduelle d'une programmation radiophonique dès 1922 confère rapidement à la musique une place centrale sur les ondes. La musique représente en effet environ 60 % du temps d'antenne dans les années 1930 et constitue le premier poste budgétaire des stations [Méadel 1991]. Cette forte présence musicale contribue à attirer très tôt l'attention du milieu musical et des critiques. Tout comme le disque, la radio suscite alors à la fois des craintes et de l'enthousiasme quant à ses usages et à ses effets [Duchesneau et Lazzaro (dir.) 2023]. Les critiques musicaux figurent parmi les plus attentifs au nouveau médium, cherchant à en penser les usages, à en encadrer les effets et à y inscrire leur expertise.

Cette contribution propose d'analyser ces dynamiques à partir du parcours d'Émile Vuillermoz (1878-1960), figure exceptionnelle par sa longévité dans l'espace médiatique, la diversité et la quantité de ses interventions dans la presse, et l'influence de ses écrits sur le milieu. Son itinéraire, qui se déploie entre presse écrite et radio, sert ici de fil conducteur pour explorer un phénomène plus large : la façon dont le milieu de la critique musicale française a accueilli, investi et cherché à institutionnaliser la radio dont l'essor ne transforme pas seulement les modes de diffusion de la musique mais reconfigure les pratiques de ceux et celles chargés d'écrire sur elle. À partir du cas de Vuillermoz, cette communication met en évidence trois principaux lieux d'interconnexion entre la presse et la radiodiffusion, soit la presse comme espace de discours sur la radio, l'implication des critiques dans les coulisses de la radio, et la reconfiguration des formes de médiation des savoirs musicaux.

La presse comme lieu de commentaire sur la radio

Dans les années 1920, il s'agit pour Vuillermoz de prendre acte de cette technologie et d'évaluer son potentiel artistique, social et politique. La presse joue ici un rôle essentiel en permettant de fixer et d'analyser un phénomène sonore éphémère. La principale tribune de Vuillermoz pour commenter spécifiquement la radio est le journal hebdomadaire *L'Impartial français*, dont il est le co-rédacteur en chef et dans les pages duquel il inaugure en janvier 1924 une première rubrique « Radio-critique », puis une seconde en novembre 1926. Vuillermoz utilise aussi la presse pour stimuler la création artistique à la radio, en lançant en mars 1924 un « Concours de radiophonie » en partenariat entre *L'Impartial français* et Radiola. Parallèlement, d'autres critiques instaurent des rubriques consacrées à la radio, contribuant à légitimer la musique radiodiffusée comme objet de commentaire esthétique, au même titre que le concert et le disque.

Les critiques ne se limitent pas à commenter les émissions : ils réfléchissent aux spécificités du médium, à ses effets sociaux et au choix des répertoires, tout en fournissant aux auditeurs des conseils pratiques (conditions d'écoute, sélection des programmes).

Leurs prises de position s'inscrivent également dans des clivages idéologiques plus larges : tandis que certains dénoncent la démocratisation induite par la radio, Vuillermoz en défend une conception éducative et civilisatrice, sous réserve d'un encadrement par des experts [Moore 2023].

Les critiques musicaux dans les coulisses de la radiodiffusion

Dans les années 1930, l'interdépendance entre presse et radio prend une nouvelle forme dans la carrière de Vuillermoz. Cette évolution s'inscrit dans un contexte de rapprochement structurel entre

presse et radiodiffusion : Vuillermoz (tout comme d'autres critiques), siège alors dans divers comités et commissions en lien avec la radiodiffusion, ce qui alimente ses textes dans la presse.

Ses tribunes dans la presse lui permettent alors de commenter et d'influencer les sujets discutés en coulisses. La presse y est aussi pour beaucoup dans son ascension dans les instances de la radiodiffusion. En effet, une interview élogieuse avec Georges Mandel, ministre des PTT, publiée dans *Excelsior* en février 1935, précède de peu sa nomination comme membre de la Section littéraire et artistique du Conseil supérieur de la Radiodiffusion.

Vuillermoz ne cesse de gravir les échelons, accédant à la présidence de la Section musicale en 1938. Sa position dans la presse sert à consolider sa position à la radio et vice-versa. Ce double rôle lui permet de jumeler deux formes de pouvoir : la sélection des œuvres destinées à la diffusion radiophonique (et les enjeux économiques associés) et leur commentaire public dans la presse. Il mobilise également ses tribunes comme levier d'action, allant jusqu'à rendre publics certains conflits afin d'influencer les décisions institutionnelles.

Un nouveau rapport à la médiation des savoirs musicaux

Un troisième niveau de convergence entre presse et radio dans le milieu musical concerne la question de la médiation des savoirs musicaux. L'investissement croissant des critiques musicaux dans la radiodiffusion reconfigure en profondeur leur rapport aux modalités de transmission des savoirs musicaux. La radio, médium de masse, impose de penser autrement les conditions de réception des œuvres, désormais écoutées par des auditeurs et auditrices qui n'ont possiblement aucune formation musicale ni même jamais assisté à un concert en salle. En effet, comme le souligne Jann Pasler, l'élargissement des publics musicaux s'accompagne d'un besoin croissant d'en encadrer la réception, en développant des formes de médiation adaptées aux nouveaux modes de diffusion [Pasler 2015, 2018]. Le critique, rompu à l'exercice d'écrire sur la musique, voit son champ d'action s'élargir : en plus de juger des œuvres, il est appelé à les rendre intelligibles au plus grand nombre.

La reconfiguration du rôle du critique se fait d'abord sur le *plan temporel*, en offrant une préparation à l'écoute. C'est dans cette optique que sont publiés des guides spécialement conçus pour les sans-filistes comme *L'Initiation à la musique : À l'usage des amateurs de radio* (Éditions du Tambourinaire, 1935) auquel Vuillermoz a contribué. Durant l'Occupation, la Radiodiffusion nationale lance son propre organe de presse où les programmes musicaux de la semaine sont commentés.

La reconfiguration du rapport à la médiation se manifeste également, sur le *plan formel*, dans l'expérimentation de formes nouvelles ou renouvelées par les ondes. Vuillermoz crée à cet égard quelques émissions, dont *L'Initiation à la musique* qu'il anime durant l'Occupation, une première fois à Marseille (zone libre) en 1941-1942. Cette émission propose des sketches dialogués entre un vieux timbalier et un jeune curieux, accompagné d'extraits musicaux. Ce format permet, d'une part, à l'auditeur néophyte de s'identifier à un jeune curieux, et, d'autre part, de décomposer le processus d'écoute et d'en rendre visibles les ressorts, le tout dans une logique clairement pédagogique. À l'automne 1943, l'émission est reprise, cette fois et captée à Paris devant un public d'adhérents aux Jeunesses musicales de France (JMF) – une association fondée en juin 1942 dont le but est d'éduquer le jeune public. En parallèle, les JMF se dotent d'un organe de presse hebdomadaire dont chaque livraison débute par un « Bloc-notes d'Émile Vuillermoz », qui revient sur différentes manifestations musicales des JMF de la semaine, dont *L'Initiation à la musique*. Ces textes prolongent dans l'espace de l'écrit le travail de médiation amorcé à la radio. Le bulletin officiel des JMF sert ainsi en quelque sorte de seconde mise en forme de l'expérience radiophonique, permettant d'en étendre la portée et d'en proposer une appropriation différée, participant à un dispositif de vulgarisation articulé entre l'oral et l'écrit.

Banni de la Radiodiffusion à la Libération, Vuillermoz se replie alors sur la presse qu'il réintègre progressivement. En septembre 1954, il lance dans le journal des JMF une nouvelle rubrique, « La page des jeunes », qui transpose à l'écrit les principes dialogués qu'il avait élaborés à la radio pour *L'Initiation à la musique* : un vieil organiste à la retraite réunit six enfants de son village, âgés de 8 à 16 ans, pour discuter de musique. Chaque rencontre est consacrée à un sujet précis, le plus souvent une œuvre, un compositeur ou une portion de l'histoire de la musique. Dans la première série de 10 textes (1954-1955), l'organiste fait découvrir des enregistrements aux enfants ; les dialogues sont

entrecoupés d'écoutes (à la manière d'un club de disque), ainsi que de fragments de partitions et de quelques illustrations, rendant le tout très attrayant. La deuxième série de 44 textes (1955-1960) reprend pour sa part peu ou prou la structure de l'*Histoire de la musique* de Vuillermoz (Fayard, 1949), délaissant les « écoutes » et les partitions, et ne conservant que les dialogues et les dessins. Il transpose ainsi à l'écrit des dispositifs élaborés à la radio, illustrant la continuité des pratiques de médiation entre les deux supports.

En conclusion, le cas de Vuillermoz symbolise une époque où l'écosystème musico-médiatique se reconfigure avec l'arrivée de la radio dont le développement s'appuie sur l'expertise développée durant plusieurs décennies dans le milieu de la critique musicale écrite.

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From the Newspaper to the Radio Age: American Foreign Correspondents, Nazi Germany, and the Cross-Media Transformation of Political Journalism

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The history of mass media in the twentieth century has long been narrated through compartmentalized perspectives that treat newspapers and radio as rival institutions. Yet the lived practices of journalists, especially foreign correspondents in Europe during the 1930s, reveal a far more entangled story of convergence and hybridization. This paper argues that the rise of American foreign correspondence in Nazi Germany provides a critical case study of how the press and radio interacted, overlapped, and transformed one another during the formative years of the “Radio Age.”

My research intervenes in three interrelated debates. First, it shows how the rise of (foreign) political journalism in the United States and the simultaneous ascent of fascist movements in Europe were deeply interconnected. American news organizations expanded their Berlin bureaus after 1933 rather than retreating, contrary to common misconceptions. Berlin, the capital of a dictatorship that immediately abolished press freedom, paradoxically became the world's most important news hub. In this sense, the United States—the self-proclaimed homeland of press freedom—was peculiarly entangled with the propaganda state it sought to cover.

Second, I highlight the pivotal role of American radio correspondents in shaping international political reporting. Figures such as Max Jordan (NBC) and William Shirer (CBS), both trained as print journalists, translated their experience into radio's immediacy and intimacy. Their broadcasts from Berlin and Munich in the late 1930s, especially during the Sudeten crisis and the Munich Agreement of 1938, established radio as the leading medium of international politics. Jordan's scoop—broadcasting the agreement to American audiences just minutes after its signing—illustrates radio's potential to bypass diplomatic channels and reconfigure the temporality of news. This moment marked a turning point in public reliance on radio for international affairs, a reliance that would only later be challenged by television in the 1960s.

Third, the paper situates these developments within a broader cross-media culture. American correspondents of the 1930s operated simultaneously across print and radio. Radio reporters were often drawn from the ranks of newspaper stars, while print journalists lent their authority and rhetorical skills to the airwaves. This permeability fostered both professional flexibility and economic opportunity, but it also blurred the boundaries of genre, style, and format. Newspapers increasingly adopted radio's vocabulary, headlines, and condensed layouts, while radio programs regularly referenced, quoted, or even staged the press. The Munich Conference once again serves as a case in point: Jordan invited Karl Henry von Wiegand, the veteran chief correspondent of Hearst's newspaper media empire, to deliver live commentary during NBC's broadcast—demonstrating how print authority was mobilized to legitimize radio news.

By following these actors and their practices, my paper contributes to the three thematic strands of the Lausanne conference:

- **Content and Formats:** I trace processes of remediation between newspapers and radio, showing how print and radio mutually shaped news genres, vocabulary, and the temporality of reporting.

- Actors and Practices: I analyze the permeability of journalistic careers, highlighting how the same individuals defined the convergent media ecosystem of the late 1930s.
- Reciprocal Representations: I investigate how newspapers covered radio (through critiques and entertainment pages) and how radio staged the press, revealing mutual recognition as both competitors and complements.

This case study contributes to an integrated history of mass media by showing that the “Radio Age” was never simply a story of radio supplanting print, but of a cross-media community in which newspapers and radio jointly produced a new form of political journalism that shaped public opinion and international politics. More broadly, the paper argues for a de-compartmentalized media history that takes seriously the simultaneity, permeability, and entanglement of different media systems, especially in moments of global crisis.

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The Magazine Plans of Public Service Broadcasters and the Audiovisual Plans of Publishers: Intersections of Radio and Press in Post-War Germany

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The "separation of powers" was considered characteristic of the media system in the Federal Republic of Germany. The victorious Western Allied powers had, with great success, established a "dual system" in West-Germany. On the one hand, radio and television were organized under public law and committed to a "public service". On the other hand, the licensing practice for newspapers and magazines created a privately organized press landscape. However, from the outset, in addition to diverse competition, there were also mutual influences and exchanges, which have hardly come into focus so far. The paper addresses such an inter-media issue starting in the second half of the 1940s and tracing a line of development up to the 1960s (Kain 2003). It sheds light on these relationships by examining two interrelated developments: 1) It focuses on the plans of public broadcasters to publish their own program previews and launch radio magazines; 2) and it highlights the much-discussed plans of publishers to gain a foothold in the broadcasting sector and offer audiovisual content in addition to print products.

The study will explore the intersections of radio and newspapers on three levels:

- Firstly, the paper specifically presents the magazine plans of the *Nordwestdeutscher Rundfunk (NWDR)*. Between May 1946 and December 1948, the radio editors Axel Eggebrecht and Peter von Zahn were also editors of the 'Nordwestdeutsche Hefte' (Schüddekopf 1980), a magazine published by *Hammerich & Lesser*. In late 1946, *NWDR* and *Axel Springer Verlag* agreed on the launch of "Hör zu!", which rapidly became West-Germany's leading radio magazine (Seegers 2001). In 1950/51, the management of the public broadcaster *NWDR* internally discussed three trial issues of a program magazine entitled "Der Hörer" (based on the model of the *BBC*-magazine "The Listener").
- Secondly, the paper presents the intermedial strategies of the "Arbeitskreis für Rundfunkfragen" (Working Group for Broadcasting Issues) in the 1950s. In this working group, editors from program magazines, news agencies, as well as representatives from business, newspaper publishers, broadcasting science, trade unions, political parties and churches repeatedly attempted to break the public service broadcasting monopoly, by advocating the introduction of commercial broadcasting and by proposing that small licenses should be granted to interested organizations and groups.
- Finally, the two case studies lead to a detailed analysis of the actor constellation, its communicative practices, and the guiding principles for a reorganization of the media landscape.

The source-critical evaluation of documents required for the study is accompanied by a pilot study. Editorial articles published in the "Hör zu!" in the 1950s on issues relating to radio and press are being examined. The *State and University Library of Hamburg* has already digitized the leading West German radio and TV magazine and made it available to a number of researchers for testing purposes. The study will therefore also serve to evaluate this digitization project.

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"Pourquoi les journalistes de la radio et la télévision suisse ne seraient-ils pas pleinement nos 'confrères' ?" (1943-1960)

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Cette citation, tirée d'un rapport présenté en 1958 au congrès de l'Association de la presse suisse (APS), donne une pleine illustration des défis que pose le développement des médias audiovisuels aux journalistes de la presse écrite. La contribution entend se concentrer sur le questionnement suivant : quels sont les enjeux soulevés en Suisse entre 1943 et 1960 par la reconnaissance corporative du statut professionnel des journalistes de la radio et de la télévision ? La reconstitution des débats suscités par l'intégration d'une nouvelle catégorie de sociétaire au sein des organisations professionnelles doit permettre d'éclairer la problématique des transferts entre médias du point de vue des protagonistes du journalisme. En parallèle, il s'agit aussi d'interroger les contours du *projet professionnel* des journalistes helvétiques, à un moment charnière de son histoire.

Pour y parvenir, deux axes d'analyse sont envisagés. En premier lieu, il importe de restituer les termes des discussions relatives à l'admission des journalistes radiophoniques, puis de la télévision, dans les associations suisses de journaliste. Sur ce plan, le cas helvétique se caractérise par un décalage important avec nombre de pays, où cette reconnaissance est actée dès les années 1930. Né dans le sillage de la mise en place par l'APS et la Société des éditeurs de journaux d'un « Registre professionnel paritaire » en 1941/1942, ce processus d'intégration débouche en 1960 sur la création d'un second registre, en partenariat cette fois-ci avec la Société suisse de radiodiffusion (SSR), spécifiquement destiné aux collaborateurs et collaboratrices des « presses parlée et télévisée ». C'est avant tout sur les années décisives de la fin des années 1950 que cette contribution souhaite porter la focale, en s'efforçant de rendre justice aux différents protagonistes du débat et à leurs points de vue. Les trajectoires et les mémoires de certains journalistes seront aussi mobilisés pour mieux comprendre le tournant que constitue cette période.

Il s'agit, d'autre part, de réinsérer ce processus d'intégration dans l'histoire de la structuration du métier de journaliste, dans un contexte d'érosion rapide, mais au rythme différencié selon les régions, de la presse d'opinion, et de croissance tout aussi rapide des médias audiovisuels à l'échelle nationale. Cette reconfiguration du champ médiatique entraîne des modifications dans les manières de concevoir les territoires professionnels du journalisme. Dans ce contexte, le cas des journalistes audiovisuels rend plus largement compte du processus de lente différenciation engagé par les membres de la profession vis-à-vis du champ politique, mais aussi des liens étroits qui unissent journalistes et éditeurs de la presse écrite, notamment dans les luttes économiques menées par ces derniers contre la SSR. Ce cas révèle également les permanences de ces efforts de distinction sociale, marqués par une « dynamique du flou » (Ruellan) dans la gestion des frontières professionnelles et un discours dénonciateur à l'égard des « amateurs ». Enfin, la spécificité du journalisme audiovisuel en Suisse, à l'essor tardif en comparaison internationale, apparaît susceptible d'offrir plus largement des points de repère dans la perspective d'une histoire transnationale des médias et du journalisme.

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L'adaptation des sujets radio pour la diffusion en ligne : chaînes de production et enjeux linguistiques

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Les médias d'information – qu'il s'agisse de presse, de radio ou de télévision – ont largement investi les possibilités de développement offertes par les technologies numériques et la diffusion en ligne (Allan 2006 ; Boczkowski 2004, 2010). Cet essor a pour effet que l'adaptation écrite de contenus produits en premier lieu pour la radio et la télévision peut entrer en relation de concurrence avec les textes publiés par les médias issus de la presse traditionnelle (Amez-Droz 2015). En Suisse, durant la première décennie du 21^e siècle, la présence notable de contenus issus des chaînes de radio et de télévision de service publique a rencontré les critiques des éditeurs privés, qui y ont vu une forme de concurrence déloyale (Mäusli et al. 2011 : 164-168). Pour régler cette situation, la concession octroyée à la Société Suisse de Radiodiffusion (SSR) précise que dans l'offre en ligne « les textes doivent indiquer à quelle émission ils se rapportent » et que dans « les contenus en ligne sans référence à une émission, les textes traitant de l'actualité, du sport ou de l'actualité régionale ou locale ne doivent pas excéder 1000 caractères » (Concession SSR, article 18, alinéa 3). En pratique, ceci implique que les journalistes en charge de la production de l'information en ligne partent des sujets radio ou télévision pour élaborer les textes à destination du site internet ou des applications pour téléphone portable. Ce phénomène d'adaptation transmédia pose plusieurs questions, parmi lesquelles celle de son effet sur les professions de l'information (disparition de certaines professions ou avènement de nouveaux métiers, notamment) et celle de ses répercussions sur les genres et formats utilisés par les journalistes pour rapporter l'actualité.

Pour répondre à ces questions, nous nous appuyons sur une recherche en cours dans les salles de rédaction de la Radio Télévision Suisse (RTS). Cette recherche mêle documentation ethnographique et analyse linguistique pour rendre compte du travail langagier des journalistes (Merminod 2025). Parmi les observables privilégiés, notre communication portera (i.) sur les chaînes de production qui se mettent en place pour assurer cette adaptation transmédia, (ii.) sur la redéfinition des tâches assignées aux journalistes dans ces processus et (iii.) sur les enjeux linguistiques que posent le passage à l'écrit d'un sujet initialement produit pour l'oral.

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